

IMPACT OF IMMIGRATION ON INTRA-INDUSTRY TRADE: AN EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FOR OECD COUNTRIES

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Abstract

Globalization has become one of the very important factors due to which countries are getting integrated with each other. Social and ethnic network have reduced transaction cost very drastically. Moreover, migration has contributed to the increase in the international trade. Also, theory has proved that migration has more impact on intra-industry trade (export and import from the same industry) than inter industry trade (export and import from different industry) so it becomes very important to study the relationship between the two variables. In this study we have tried to find out the relationship between immigration and Intra-Industry trade for 25 OECD countries. Data has been collected from the year 1999-2017 based on the availability of the data. Balanced panel data model has been used in the study to establish the relationship between Intra-Industry trade and Immigration. The study found that there exists no significant relationship between immigration and Intra-Industry trade and thereby it contradicts the other studies. However, the study supports the theory that immigration helps trade by reducing the trade transaction cost. Moreover, the study found that there exists negative relationship between capital labour ratio and Intra-Industry trade.

Keywords: Intra-Industry trade, Immigration, OECD, Capital Labour ratio

JEL Classifications:

1. Introduction

Intra-industry trade (IIT) and its relationship with immigration form a crucial facet of international trade dynamics. IIT refers to the exchange of similar industry products between countries, where both exports and imports occur within the same industry. This stands in contrast to Inter-Industry Trade, where products from different industries are exchanged. A notable example of IIT is the United States simultaneously producing and exporting automobiles while importing automobiles from other countries. The existence of IIT is contingent on substantial product differentiation and economies of scale within the industries (Krueger, 1978). IIT can be categorized into horizontal and vertical IIT. Horizontal IIT involves the exchange of similar technologies, where there is minimal technological disparity between traded goods. On the other hand, vertical IIT occurs when trade involves varying technological levels (Helpman and Krugman, 1985). The Grubel and Lloyd index serves as a key theoretical tool to measure the intensity of IIT. A value close to one implies high IIT intensity, whereas a value close to zero indicates low IIT intensity (Grubel & Lloyd, 1971). IIT levels are generally higher in developed nations due to extensive product differentiation and economies of scale. In contrast, developing countries exhibit lower IIT levels, often driven by vertical integration (Manrique, 1987). A positive correlation between IIT and economic development exists, implying that IIT can be an influential factor in a country's development (Bhattacharya, 2007).

Among developed countries, horizontal IIT predominates, especially in countries like the USA and European nations, where technological disparities in traded goods are minimal (Manrique, 2007).

Vertical IIT, on the other hand, is gaining prominence in countries like South Korea and correlates positively with economic development (Bhattacharya, 2005).

Immigration and IIT also share a relationship. Immigration fosters trade by establishing networks in destination countries and facilitating trade between countries with lower tariff rates. Studies have shown a positive correlation between immigration and IIT, such as in Spain (Blanes, 2005). The dynamics of immigration and trade in the OECD, comprising 36 member countries, further demonstrate the intertwined nature of these processes.

The OECD, founded in 1961, serves as a platform for member countries to accelerate trade and achieve economic growth. Its members, predominantly developed nations, engage in high levels of trade (OECD). In recent years, OECD countries have witnessed an increase in permanent migrants, particularly in European OECD nations and the United States (OECD, International Migration Outlook). This influx has led to adjustments in labour migration programs and initiatives aimed at integrating new migrants (Bowen & Wu, 2013).

However, the relationship between immigration and IIT in OECD countries is more nuanced than often assumed. This paper contradicts previous studies by suggesting that there is no significant relationship between immigration and IIT in OECD countries. Yet, it posits that

immigration can reduce trade transaction costs and offers insights into how immigration can positively impact IIT, highlighting the complex and evolving dynamics of global trade and migration.

2. Theoretical Background

Krugman (1979) has come up with the concept of product differentiation and returns to the scale that results in the trade between two or more than two nations. Prior to this most of the trade theory talked about trade between two or more than two nations because of inter-industry. Also, most of the classical and neo-classical theory has a particular assumption that there is no factor mobility outside the country, though there is factor mobility within the country. However, Krugman (1979), found that factor can be mobile across the entire world, and mobility depends on the wage rate.

There are basically two ways through which immigrants can increase trade. Firstly, immigrant can create a network in the home country markets by knowing properly its market structure and thus having a proper knowledge of peoples need. Moreover, people migrating into host country may demand for certain products which might be available only in their own country. So, the preference for their home country product may increase host countries import from the home country. Secondly, immigrants can also increase host countries exports and imports, if immigrants come to the host country with business contacts and with the knowledge of the business and political environment of the country. Globerman (2001)

However, whether the preference and network effect have positive or negative effect on trade is unclear.

Moreover, most of the literature suggest that, immigration will reduce trade transaction cost. Also, existing literature suggest that transaction cost will vary with the products. Rauch (1999) argues that the effect of immigration in reducing trade transaction cost is very high when there exists product differentiation. White (2008) argues that, the preference for home country goods will increase trade for differentiated goods, instead of homogeneous goods as for homogeneous goods there is a higher probability that the substitute of the goods will be available in the host country. In other words, preference for home country goods will increase Intra-Industry trade.

3. Review of literature

Intra-Industry Trade (IIT) is a pivotal concept in international economics, referring to the exchange of the same or similar commodities by a single country. It stands as a cornerstone of traditional trade theories such as the theory of absolute and comparative advantage. Balassa (1966) was among the first to provide an index to measure IIT, and Grubel and Lloyd (1975) subsequently introduced an alternative index. However, Lipsey (1976) argued that IIT is primarily a statistical concept, thereby challenging its philosophical underpinnings.

IIT's growing significance globally is evident. Veeramani (2002) identified an increase in IIT levels across most manufacturing sectors, except for gems and jewellery. This trend extends to developing countries, as highlighted by Manrique (1987). IIT not only contributes to the quantity but also significantly impacts product quality (Ito & Okubo, 2016). It plays a crucial role in overall economic development.

Research has revealed positive correlations between GNP per capita, the size of the manufacturing sector, and the intensity of IIT (Bhattacharyya, 2007). Economic development is further linked to partner countries and IIT (Bhattacharyya, 2005), with IIT facilitating job creation and technological transfer. Thus, IIT is a central focus of new trade theories.

Government policies, such as liberalization processes in India, have spurred IIT by enabling industries to capitalize on economies of scale and product differentiation (Bagchi, 2018). Regional trade agreements have also played a role in intensifying IIT among member countries (Menon & Dixon, 1996). Negotiations and reductions in trade barriers have likewise positively influenced IIT (Bano, 2002). In an increasingly globalized world, IIT remains essential not only for economic development but also for financial and economic stability.

IIT's impact extends to labour mobility and market stability. It affects the movement of labour between industries and occupations (Brülhart, Elliott & Lindley, 2006), is positively associated with foreign direct investment and product differentiation but negatively associated with labour intensity (Kandogan, 2003). Additionally, IIT can create new divisions of labour and influence wage volatility (Caetano & Galego, 2006; Brülhart & Elliott, 2002). While IIT can foster innovation and economies of scale (Ruffin, 1999), it has also been linked to increased wage inequality (Beaulieu, Benarroch & Gaisford, 2004). The connection between trade and immigration is another area of exploration. Bowen and Wu (2013) argued that immigration increases the

output of non-traded commodities, particularly in OECD countries. They noted a complementary relationship between trade and immigration. Similarly, Ortega and Peri (2011) found a positive effect of immigration on trade in OECD countries, enhancing employment rates. Lewer (2000) observed a significant relationship between immigration and trade in 16 OECD countries, suggesting a positive impact of immigration on bilateral trade flows.

Several studies have sought to understand the relationship between migration and IIT. White (2008) discovered a positive relationship between IIT and the stock of immigrants in the United States, with horizontal IIT being more prominent. Blanes (2005) also found a positive connection between IIT and immigration in Spain, with more IIT occurring with developed countries. Leitao (2013) highlighted a positive relationship between IIT and migration between Portugal and the European Union, emphasizing how immigration can reduce trade transaction costs.

These studies collectively underline the intricate relationships between IIT, trade, and immigration, shedding light on the complex dynamics that shape global commerce and labour mobility.

4. Research Gap

Existing literature have considered only one country for showing the linkage of Immigration and Intra-Industry trade. Very few literatures have taken some groups of countries or blocs to examine the relationship between immigration and Intra-Industry trade. As Intra-Industry trade is more evident in developed countries so there are very few countries which considered some groups of developed

countries to examine the link between immigration and Intra Industry trade. There are very few literatures which tries to examine the relationship between intra-industry trade and that of immigration with respect to OECD countries.

4.1. Research Question

Whether immigration can boost intra-industry trade in OECD countries?

Is there any positive relationship between intra-Industry trade and GDP per capita?

Does factor endowment have any impact on intra-industry trade?

4.2. Research Objectives

To check if there exist any relationship between Intra-Industry trade, immigration, GDP per capita and factor endowment.

4.3. Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is a relationship between Intra Industry trade and migration

Many literatures have argued that there exists a positive relationship between Immigration and Intra Industry trade.

Hypothesis 2: Trade transaction cost reduces the volume of Intra Industry trade

This hypothesis argues that there is a negative relationship between trade transaction cost and the volume of Intra Industry trade.

Hypothesis 3: There exists a relationship between Economic development and Intra Industry trade Literature suggested that there exists a positive relationship between Economic development and Intra Industry trade. This paper considers GDP per capita for measuring economic development.

Hypothesis 4: There exists a significant relationship between Intra-Industry trade and capital labour ratio

It is not sure whether there is a negative or positive relationship between the two. Blanes (2005) suggested that capital labour ratio has positive impact on vertical Intra-Industry trade and negative on horizontal Intra Industry trade. But as in the given study we are considering the total IIT so we are not sure about the sign.

5. Data and Methodology

For the study secondary data is used. The time frame is taken from 1996-2017. For measuring Intra Industry trade Grubel Lloyd index has been used which is consider as the most widely employed measure for IIT. We calculate it by adjusting it for categorical aggregation and the data at the 3-digit level of SITC (revised 3) for all the 25 countries and their partners by taking weighted average of all the sectors.

$$GL_j = \left[1 - \left(\frac{|x_j - m_j|}{x_j + m_j} \right) \right] * 100$$

Where m and X are bilateral imports and exports of all the 25 OECD countries and its partner country.

The specific functional form which we used in the paper is as follows:

$$\ln IIT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln im + \beta_2 \ln \frac{K}{l} + \beta_3 \ln GDP + \beta_4 \ln TC + u$$

Were,

IIT= Intra-Industry Trade

im=Immigration

K/l= capital labour ratio

GDP= GDP per capita

TC= Transaction Cost (Cost insurance Freight/Free on Board)

u= Error term

Moreover, all the variables are measured in natural log. In the model im is the variable for immigration measured by stock of immigration for all the 25 countries, K/L is the capital

labour ratio of all the 25 countries, where, capital is measured by gross capital formation and labour is measured by total labour employed. GDP is GDP per capita of the 25 countries and TC is transaction cost measured by the ratio of Cost Insurance Freight and Free on board. The measure of transaction cost based on CIF/FOB ration has been given by De (2006).

According to Helpman (1987) and Blanes (2006) the model predicts b_1 , b_3 to be positive and b_2 , b_4 to be negative. The reason for the same has been already explained. The model will be interpreted in terms of elasticity because of the natural logarithm value. 25 OECD countries are taken into consideration which have been selected based on GDP per capita. Top 5 trading partners for each of the OECD countries are taken into consideration. Export and import data are collected from WITS, immigration data is collected from OECD stats, CIF/FOB data is collected from IMF (Direction of trade statistics) and GDP per capita, gross capital formation, total labour force employed are collected from world Bank.

6. Analysis and Results

Following the huge body of the literature some additional variable has been added in the study to examine the relationship between Intra-Industry Trade and migration. To find the relationship between Intra-Industry trade and migration panel data analysis has been conducted. Panel data analysis has three approaches, namely pooled OLS, fixed effect model and random effect model. In pooled OLS individuals have no unique attributes. Whereas in fixed effect model individuals have unique attributes that

do not vary over time. Lastly in random effect model individuals have unique and time constant attributes of individuals and these are not correlated with the individual regressors. Several tests are used to determine the best approach. In the current study we have used Breusch-Pagan LM test and Hausman test to find the best model, and based on these tests we concluded that fixed effect model is the best model for the study.

As explained earlier, data has been collected from the period 1999-2017 based on the availability of the data. Stationarity of the data is something which is very crucial for panel data analysis. Here in the given study, we have done unit root or stationarity test of the data to exclude the biases related to the stationarity.

Table 1: Levin-Lin-Chu test of Unit root

Variables	Fixed Effect without trend	Fixed Effect with trend
Intra-Industry Trade	-2.67**	-4.49**
Migration	-4.63**	-5.77**
K/L	-4.97**	-4.96**
CIF/FOB	-2.70**	-3.63**
GDP Per capita	-3.24**	-3.21**

Note: In the LL test for unit root the data has unit root test root test under null hypothesis, where under alternative hypothesis it has a stationary.

** indicates significance of the result. In the table above we can see the result of Levin-Lin-Chu test of unit root. According to this test under null hypothesis the data has unit root, whereas, under alternative

hypothesis the data is stationary. As from the result we can say that all the variables are stationary at level one as the results for all the variable are significant. So, we can safely say that the model can be applied without performing any of the co-integration test.

Table 2 provides the result of our analysis and it shows the relationship between immigration and intra-industry trade for OECD countries. Before going into the main result, it is first important to find out the appropriate model for our analyse. In the given paper we did two tests to find the appropriate model which are Lagrange multiplier test and Hausman test. Firstly, by interpreting the result of langrage multiplier test we can say that random effect model is more appropriate than pooled OLS as the result is significant and thereby, we reject the null hypothesis that there is no random effect. Secondly by interpreting the result of Hausman test we can say that fixed effect is more appropriate than random effect as the result is significant, so we go with the fixed effect model.

The estimation result of fixed effect is given below. The double logarithm of the model allows us to interpret the coefficient as elasticities. Firstly, by looking at the test result we can say that all the coefficient values are not equal to zero and the model is perfectly fit. Now looking at the overall R square value which is 40% we can say that the model is moderately fit.

Table 2: Panel Data Analyse

Dependent Variable Intra-Industry Trade			
Effect	OLS	Fixed Effect	Random Effect

Migration	0.06** (.01)	0.002 (.0070)	.003 (.0070)
K/L	.116** (0.11)	-.038** (.0094)	-.023** (.0085)
CIF/FOB	-.027 (.03)	-.0647** (.0238)	-0.48** (.0232)
Gdp Per capita	-.09** (.015)	.00331 (.0410)	-.069** (.0336)
Constant	-.085 (.18)	.11250 (.3402)	.64933** (.2885)
R Sq	0.37	0.40	
F Test		13.79(0.00)	
Wald Test			46.90(0.00)
LM test			2992(0.00)
Hausman test			22.00(0.00)
No of Obs.	475	475	475

Note: ** indicates significance level at 95% level confidence interval (p-value <0.05)

Now coming to the main part of our analyse that is the relationship between migration and intra-industry trade we can say from our fixed effect model that the coefficient value of migration is not significant even though it is positive, which signifies that there is no significant relationship between migration and Intra-Industry trade. However, if we see the literature, many literatures have already proved that there exists a positive relationship between migration and Intra-Industry trade. However, this study contradicts all the literature as it is seen that there exists no positive relationship between Intra-Industry trade and migration. There could be many possible reasons behind non-significance relationship between migration and Intra-Industry trade.

This study investigates the relationship between Intra-Industry trade (IIT) and several key variables within 25 OECD

countries. It's essential to recognize that the relationship between these variables may vary among countries, as different studies often focus on individual nations.

One reason for varying results could be data-related. This study primarily examines the import and export of commodities, while OECD data from 2019 highlights that many immigrants are engaged in the service sector, particularly outsourcing. In addition, a significant percentage of immigrants aged 15-24 are not employed but rather engaged in education or training, especially in the European Union.

Another factor is the trade policies of OECD countries. The presence of tariff and non-tariff barriers plays a crucial role. Non-OECD countries, many of which are developing or least developed, are the primary trading partners of OECD nations. These non-OECD countries often maintain high tariff rates, which can significantly reduce overall trade, including IIT. Furthermore, even when tariff rates decrease, non-tariff barriers, such as sanitary and phytosanitary measures, can hinder trade. These measures are commonly applied to animal and plant products in OECD countries.

Regarding the capital-labor ratio variable, the study reveals a significant negative relationship with IIT. This outcome aligns with existing research, although the specific nature of this relationship remains uncertain. Previous work, such as Blanes (2005), suggested that capital-labor ratios have a positive relationship with vertical IIT and a negative relationship with horizontal IIT. However, this study considers total IIT, which can be influenced by the developed nature of most OECD countries and their trading

partners, potentially leading to horizontal IIT.

For the Cost Insurance Freight/Free on Board (CIF/FOB) ratio, there is a significant negative relationship with IIT, supporting the theory that reducing trade transaction costs can increase trade volume.

Lastly, the study finds no significant relationship between GDP per capita and IIT, although the coefficient is positive. This differs from the broader literature, which suggests a positive relationship between GDP per capita and IIT. The variability in the findings may stem from the complex interplay of factors affecting IIT within the unique context of the OECD countries studied.

7. Conclusion and Suggestion

This paper uses panel data regression to model Intra-Industry trade. To examine the relationship between Intra-Industry trade and migration for the OECD countries, this paper collects data from the period 1999 to 2017 based on the availability of the data. The result shows that there is no significant relationship between Intra-Industry trade and migration and thereby it contradicts other studies. However, this paper support the theory that immigration helps trade by reducing the trade transaction cost. Also the paper argues that there is a significant negative relationship between Intra-Industry trade and Cost Insurance Freight/ Free on Board ratio and Intra-Industry trade. The paper further suggests that there is a horizontal Intra-Industry trade between the OECD countries and its trading partner as there is a negative relationship between the two variables and also as most of the top trading partners of the OECD countries are developed nations.

However, the paper suggests that there is no relationship between GDP per capita and Intra-Industry trade.

So, it becomes very crucial for the OECD countries to come with a policy which can increase the Intra-Industry trade. As flows of migration in OECD countries is very high so all the OECD countries should try to grab maximum advantage of it. It is necessary for all the OECD countries to decrease the level of both tariff and non-tariff barriers and thereby increasing the volume of Intra-Industry trade. Moreover, as according to OECD international migration outlook 2019, most of the migrants are engaged in tertiary sector so it becomes very crucial for all the OECD countries to make the other sectors attracting for the migrants so that migrants are uniformly scattered across all the sectors and thereby makes Intra-Industry trade more significant.

8. References

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